

WEAR RESISTANCE INFLUENCERS OF PARTICLE REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITE

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1 Introduction

A particle reinforced composite material consisting of the unsaturated polyester resin and the fine dispersion of aluminium hydroxide has good mechanical and physical properties. It performs well as laboratory or culinary bench top, in bathrooms as vanity top or sanitary ware, in maritime and agricultural applications. One of the dominant requirements for these products is wear resistance. Good wear resistance is the cornerstone for commercial success.

It is important to know which of the many components of the composite material have biggest impact on the wear properties. Besides the composition one must not forget the post curing process that is done to obtain extensive crosslinking and enhance the mechanical and physical properties of the polymer composite.

The aim of the current research was to enhance the wear resistance of a particle filled polymer composite. The objective was to study which components and technological process parameters influence this property. Since hardness and toughness are inversely related increased wear resistance is accompanied by reduced impact resistance. [1] Further aim of this research is to find the compromise between hard phase and tough matrix to avoid brittleness.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Isophthalic acid and neopentyl glycol based unsaturated polyester resin (UP), aluminum hydroxide (ATH) with fine particle size and bulk density of 1000 kg/m³, Mohs' hardness index of 2.5...3.5 and silica with particle size fractions

0...0.8, bulk density of 1450...1550 kg/m³, Mohs' hardness index of 7 were the main components used in the composite material. [2] [3]

Methyl ethyl ketone peroxide based peroxide mixture was added with ratio of 1/100 wt% for curing.

In order to accurately imitate commercial materials and physical processes a TiO based color pigment was included in the composition.

2.2 Fabrication

Test specimens were fabricated with vacuum assisted extruder. Vacuum removes air from the dispersion and helps to achieve a non-porous material.

The dispersion was casted into aluminum molds. The mold cavity was a 5x5 mm square with a height of 40 mm. This corresponded to the wear test specimen. The aim was to fabricate ready-made test specimens and avoid cutting and other post-treatment steps that could affect the material properties.

The specimens for testing material's surface indentation hardness were casted into closed mould measuring 300x300x10 mm. This helped to achieve equal thickness and planar surfaces.

The test specimens were given different thermal post treatment. Some of the specimens were cured at room temperature for 12 h and others were post cured at 40 °C or 60 °C for 12 h. A conventional thermal oven was used for elevated temperature post curing.

Table 1 summarizes the variation of components in different test specimens.

2.3 Testing

GYZJ 934-1 Barcol Impressor was used to measure the indetation hardness of the material surface. The

indentation hardness test was conducted according to ASTM D 2583-13 “Standard test method for indentation hardness of rigid plastics by means of a Barcol Impressor”. The Barcol Impressor is developed for testing fabricated parts and test specimens. It is well suited for reinforced plastics. It enables quick and simple ranking of materials by surface hardness. [4] Surface hardness is a signal of percentage of cure of a polymer composite but also depends from the concentration of filler material and the type of filler material. [5] The Barcol Impressor was also used because there is data from earlier research work that can be compared and reanalyzed. Wear tests were conducted according to ASTM G132 – 96 (2007) “Standard test method for pin abrasion testing”. The main value of this test method is the relative ranking of materials. This standard utilizes test method where measurable mass loss occurs and it is intended for material applications where moderate to severe abrasion is observed. The test method does not attempt to replicate the conditions that the material may experience in service. [6] The service conditions are hard to predict and are not the scope of this research. The aim is to compare different material compositions and their influence to material wear properties. The test conditions were chosen based on earlier experience and preliminary tests. The preliminary tests were conducted to assure that the wear mechanism of the material is same throughout the test and is not influenced by friction induced heat or other factors. Three different test durations were considered: 45 sec, 90 sec and 180 sec. No change was observed. Normal load of 1 N and 3 N was tested. Also incidence was varied. In sake of comparability the same test conditions were chosen as G. Zhao, I. Hussainova, M. Antonov et al. used in their study of friction and wear of fiber reinforced polyimide composites because preliminary tests assured the suitability of these parameters. [7] The Universal Macro Materials Test equipment (UMT-2) CETR Bruker was used for conducting the wear tests. A Pin-on-Flat configuration with sliding speed of 0.1 m s⁻¹ and a load of 1 N was used. The pin movement amplitude was 25 mm and the frequency was 2 Hz. Test duration was 3 min. In order to avoid clogging of the abrasive surface the surface was continuously shifted with overall displacement of 70 mm. The abrasive was changed after each test. A P400 (35 μm) silicon carbide abrasive paper was used as the abrasive surface. The material wear during the reciprocating tests was measured as loss of mass. The initial and final

weight was measured with 0.1 mg accuracy. The test specimens were cleaned from debris with compressed air before weighting and mounting to the pin holder.

The test specimen measurements were 5x5x20 mm where the 5x5 mm square was the contact area with the abrasive surface. All the specimens had a run-in test to assure a full contact surface with the abrasive surface. There were 3 tests with each specimen.

In order to calculate the wear rate the density of the different specimens was measured. A kit of analytical scale and a jig was used to weight the mass of the specimen in air and fluid according to the Archimedes method. The density is determined by equation:

$$\rho = \frac{m_{s\bar{a}} \cdot \rho_v}{m_{s\bar{a}} - m_{sv}} \quad (1)$$

ρ – specimen density

$m_{s\bar{a}}$ – specimen weight in air

m_{sv} – specimen weight in fluid

ρ_v – density of the fluid

Water was used as the fluid.

All the tests were conducted at room temperature 22±2 °C and relative humidity of 40...60%.

2.4 Assessment of wear

The amount of wear can be expressed directly or indirectly. Direct wear quantities are the loss of mass, change in geometrical dimensions or change in volume of the wearing body.

The loss of material of a tribological element can be determined by weighting it before and after testing. There exists danger that the micro contact geometry will change during disassembly and reassembly of the test specimen. Moreover, the debris present in the contact zone will be disrupted or removed. Interruption of the test may influence the mechanism of wear. Care must be taken that the mass loss is due to wear and not due to other phenomena like the absorption or loss of water of the composite material. [8] [9]

Continuous monitoring of wear is frequently done through on-line measuring of changes in linear dimensions. This gives info about the evolution of the wear and does not interrupt the test. This is done through measuring the distance between the mounting fixtures of the two tribo elements. This

can also lead to misinterpretation because of material transfer from one element to another that can reduce, eliminate or increase the measured distance. Inductive or capacitive sensors are the frequent choice for real-time measurements of change in linear dimensions. The choice depends from the environmental conditions and necessary accuracy. [9]

The volume loss from a test specimen can be derived from the mass loss in case the material is a known value. Nevertheless, sometimes it is hard to determine the density for example when dealing with coated or surface treated materials. Other possibility is to derive the volume loss from dimensional change. There is a relatively easy equation for calculating wear for reciprocating sliding test with ball-on-disc or pin-on-plate. [9] [10]

The Archard wear relationship (specific wear rate) is a universal quantitative parameter of wear. It is the worn volume of material divided by the introduced mechanical energy. The contact energy is the outcome of the load and distance. [8] [11]

$$K = \frac{V}{F \cdot s} \quad (2)$$

K – specific wear rate coefficient

V – wear volume

F – normal load

s – sliding distance

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Indentation hardness

The indentation hardness of the material was measured with Barcol impressor. The increase of filler material increases the hardness compared to the neat resin as can be observed from Fig. 3. The same trend has been seen in earlier studies. The increase is nearly 50 %. This can be contributed to the higher hardness of the filler material compared to the neat resin. [12]

Also the curing at elevated temperature improves the indentation harness. Curing at 60 °C for 12 h improves the indentation hardness compared to room temperature cure 37 %. Post-curing at higher temperature leads to more cross linked material and thus improves the mechanical properties. [5]

The silica reinforced composite showed a Barcol Impressor value of 70 whereas comparable aluminum hydroxide reinforced test specimen had

indentation hardness of 49. This can be attributed to the higher Mohs' hardness index of the silica (7) compared to the Mohs' hardness index of 3.5 of the aluminium hydroxide. Although the Mohs' index of aluminium hydroxide is 50 % from the silica index the indentation hardness of the aluminium hydroxide reinforced composite is 70 % of the hardness of the silica reinforced composite. This tells that also the components with lower hardness contribute to the hardness of the composite.

There was not observed any difference in the hardness of neat resin and neat resin with TiO.

3.2 Mass loss

There are several arguments that do not support the measurement of wear through the weighting of the lost mass. These include the altering of the contact surface and wear mechanism during test stops, mass fluctuation due to environmental conditions and debris removal from the contact area. [9] Nevertheless, if all these conditions are considered while setting up the test then the results can be reliable. The particle reinforced composite material in current study has a significant mass loss (more than 1 mg) during one run so the mass loss can be measured with high accuracy.

The components of the composite have different densities and due to that also different compositions of material have different densities as described in Table 3. The loss of mass gives misleading information of the wear properties as the same weight of material has different volume due to difference in density.

This can be easily seen from Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. The mass of lost material increases as the wt% of filler in the composition increases. Nevertheless, the actual amount of lost material decreases due to the fact that density of the filler is higher than the density of the resin.

3.3 Wear rate

The wear rate was calculated according to the equation (2).

Fig. 5 shows that the wear rate decreases 14 % when aluminium hydroxide is added to the casting dispersion. The change in filler wt% does not have linear relation to wear rate but the absolute values are very close.

Same trend can be observed when we look at Fig. 6 that represents the wear rate and curing conditions relationship. A more cross-linked material has lower wear rate. The wear rate is reduced by 24 % if the material is cured at 60 °C.

As was observed with indentation hardness the filler type has major impact on wear rate. There are other influencers besides filler hardness but hardness gives a good indication of the wear rate. With silica filler we see a dramatic drop of 88 % in wear rate. Also TiO contributes to wear rate although there was not any measurable difference in hardness between neat resin and specimen with TiO addition. TiO increases the wear rate 5 %.

4 Conclusions

The tests showed that with higher concentration of filler the wear resistance increases. A sample with 55 wt.% of filler had 14 % better results then compared to neat resin. This is due to the higher hardness of the aluminium hydroxide compared to the unsaturated polyester resin. The filler concentration is limited by the flow parameters of the casting dispersion.

Post curing has also positive effect on the wear resistance. The rise of wear resistance correlates to the increase of other mechanical properties. Post curing at 60°C for 12 h increases the wear resistance of the material by 24 % compared to room temperature cured material. It is the optimum temperature when considering stain resistance, mechanical properties and cost.

Filler type has major contribution to the wear rate as silica reinforced specimen performs 88 % better than aluminium hydroxide reinforced one.

Also components with smaller overall concentration like TiO influence the wear rate.

There is a correlation between material hardness and wear rate although with some reservations.

Good wear resistance properties of particle reinforced composite material are obtainable.

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Materials	KK-1 (wt.%)	KK-2 (wt.%)	KK-3 (wt.%)	KK-4 (wt.%)	KK-5 (wt.%)	KK-6 (wt.%)	KK-7 (wt.%)	KK-8 (wt.%)
Resin	100	35	45	40	40	40	40	100
Filler	0	65	55	60	60	60	60	0
Filler type	-	ATH	ATH	ATH	ATH	ATH	Silica	-
Catalyst	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
TiO	0	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Table 1. Composition of test specimens

Factor	KK-1	KK-2	KK-3	KK-4	KK-5	KK-6	KK-7	KK-8
Curing temp. (°C)	40	40	40	40	22	60	40	40
Curing time (h)	12	12	12	12	12	12	12	12

Table 2. Curing conditions

Property	KK-1	KK-2	KK-3	KK-4	KK-5	KK-6	KK-7	KK-8
Density (g/cm ³)	1,20	1,74	1,62	1,64	1,64	1,64	2,02	1,19

Table 3. Test specimen densities

Fig. 1 Mass loss of specimen with different wt% of filler

Fig. 3 Barcol Impressor relation to wt% of filler

Fig. 2 Volume loss of specimen with different wt% of filler

Fig. 4 Barcol Impressor relation to curing temp.

Fig. 5 Wear rate of specimens with different wt% of filler

Fig. 7 TiO influence on wear rate

Fig. 6 Wear rate relation to curing temp.

Fig. 8 Filler type and thus hardness influence on wear rate

Fig. 9 Reciprocating sliding jig

Fig. 10 Casted material specimen for Barcol impressor